

Survey of brain tumor detection using Machine Learning: A comparative approach

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Abstract—Brain tumor is a dreadful tumor. Accurate and prompt diagnosis of brain tumor is essential for implementing an effective treatment of this disease. The choice of a treatment modality depends on the stage of tumor at the time of diagnosis, the pathological type and grade of the tumor. Computer-aided diagnosis (CAD) based tumor detection is an extensively researched topic as Manual detection is time consuming and for the vast number of patient it is quite impossible to detect the tumor without an error. Machine learning has been of great help in many medical applications and can be used as a classifier in the early detection of the tumor present in brain. In this paper, a survey and analysis of the various machine learning approaches that have been implemented for the diagnosis of brain tumor is done. The survey paper draws a comparison of the various existing techniques for the prediction of brain tumor using medical data and points out their advantages and shortcomings.

I. INTRODUCTION

The human brain consists of the supportive tissues and nerve cells similar to the meninges and glial cells. They control brainstem activities like breathing, movement of the muscles cerebellum (walk), sense, cerebrum (personality), thinking and emotions. Primary tumors can be benign (cancerous) and cancerous (malignant). The cancerous cell begins anywhere in the body and also rapidly growing in the brain.

The main symptoms of brain tumors rely on their location and size. The common indications are headaches, changes in the mood and personality, trouble speaking, difficulties in walking, vomiting, and high blood pressure. Ophthalmologists classify the tumors into different grades (I-IV). The common such tumor types in the children are medulloblastoma, Grade I, Grade II (Glioma), ependymoma and glioma brainstem. Gliomas are kinds of brain lesions with greatest prevalence and death rate. These types of tumors are characterized by high-grade glioma (HGG) and low-grade glioma (LGG). Even under the treatment the average patient's survival rate is more than 14 months subsequent to diagnosis.

Recent treatments for tumor detection are radiotherapy, surgery, chemotherapy, and a mixture of them. Characterization of the tumor region is more difficult due to spatially heterogeneity of the neoplastic tissues. Currently, brain tumor diagnosis is histopathologic analysis such as resection and surgical biopsy. But it has some limitations such as interpretation variability and sampling error. Several studies use MR spectroscopy for the prediction of a brain tumor. The machine learning approaches are utilized for tumor detection, but accurate tumor detection

is an intricate task due to variability in tumor location and appearance. [3]

II. RELATED WORK

Artificial intelligence is an emerging field in computer science which deals with performing task of human intelligence without actual intervention of any human being. It is widely accepted by that any form of intelligence is an outcome of experience and learning. Thus it is primitive that to acquire intelligence the computer learns from available data in the concerned field. After the outbreak of the digital revolution, the collection and storing of data in the field of medical science gained considerable impetus.

Thereby, overcoming one of the major shortcomings for the application of machine learning in the field of medical science. support vector machine is among the machine learning algorithms widely used in brain tumor detection and other medical data processing.

Support vector machine

The problem statements for which support vector machine has been employed largely consists of regression, classification into single or multiclass and outliers detection. Support vector machine have been primarily divided into two process - solving a quadratic equation and predicting the position of the hyper plane. In the initial period well established, pre-existing quadratic optimization algorithms were used for this process. This approach worked perfectly for small data sets comprising of around 1000 samples. Their advantage is that they are not designed to meet specific requirements and hence require lesser input from the developer as well as they provide high numeric precision. In case of larger datasets and when the kernel does not fit into the memory requirement, a more customized algorithm has to be employed that take into consideration a broader spectra of aspects.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

The review of literature presents a brief description of the existing researches on machine learning techniques used for the detection of brain tumor. The narration of the various algorithms and approaches used is presented in the review. S. Deepak et al. [3] have analyzed MRI data using CNN, SVM and KNN model. The dataset from Figshare was used to classify three types of cancer Meningioma, Glioma, and pituitary.

TABLE I
COMPARISON THE VARIOUS SURVEYED APPROACHES

Publisher	dataset	software	Model	Image classification method description	Accuracy	Classified as
S. Deepak, P.M. Ameer et al. [3] (2019)	MRI dataset from figshare	MATLAB 2018b	pre-trained deep network, the GoogLeNet via transfer learning	i) Transfer learned deep CNN model ii) Deep CNN features with SVM iii) Deep CNN features with KNN	98% i) transfer model 92.3% ii) Deep CNN 97.8% (SVM) ii)Deep CNN 98.8% (KNN)	Meningioma Glioma, pituitary
Amhad Rehman et al. (2020) [6]	Three BraTS datasets 2015, 2017,2018		Deep learning based method 3-D CNN and correlation along FNN based automated approach (proposed CNN)	i) new CNN architecture based brain tumor extraction ii) pretrained VGG19 based deep features extraction iii) pearson correlation along with FNN features selection for final classification	98.32% (2015) , 96.97% (2017), 92.67% (2018)	Flair , T1CE, T1, T2 categorized
Ahmet Cinar et al. (2020) [2]	Dataset from the kaggle site (MRI images)	Matlab	Resnet50 architecture (CNN) as base, Alexnet, Densenet201, InceptionV3 and Googlenet models	Hybrid CNN architecture	97.2%	Tumors or no tumors
Javaria Amin et al. (2020) [1]	BRATS datasets (2012-2015)		Stacked sparse autoencoder (SSAE) model	i) High pass and median filter ii) Seed growing method iii) SSAE model with a softmax layer for classification	100% (2012) 92% (2012 synthetic), 95% (2013)' 100% (leaderboard 2013), 97% (2014) 95% (2015)	Tumors or no tumors
Mesut et al. (december 2019) [7]	Collected by field experts (doctors, radiologists) and shared on internet	Matlab (R2019a)	New CNN model named BrainMRNet models (AlexNet, GoogleNet, VGG-16)	BrainMRNet CNN model using AlexNet, GoogleNet, VGG-16	96.05% (BrainMRNet)	Tumors or no tumors
Thiruvankadam kalaiselvi et al. (August 2019) [4]	BraTS2013 and whole brain atlas data sets	keras 2.2.1, tensorFlow 2.0, and python 3.5	CNN model	i) predictive cognitive system ii) kalaiselvi's method iii) statistical method iv) Hybrid method v) Avinash's method vi) Wavelet metod vii) proposed method	89%	Tumor classification
Fatih ozyurt et al. (2020) [5]	Cancer Genome Atlas Glioblastoma multiform (TCGA-GBM) database		fuzy C-mean (SR-FCM-CNN) using SqueezeNet architecture (using FCM algorithm)	feature extracted and pretrained SqueezeNet architecture from CNN architecture and classified with extreme learning machine	98.33%	benign and malignant tumor

The author showed KNN model works better and SVM classified the tumor correctly. The author claimed the system recorded the best classification accuracy compared to all the related works. AMJAD rehman et al. [6] proposed classification using a 3-D convolutional neural network (CNN) architecture. Three BraTS data sets were used to extract and feature extraction. A comparison with existing techniques was shown to show the comparable accuracy. Ahmet cinar et al. [2] used Resnet50 as base architecture and kaggle datasets used for the work. With the model the author claimed 97.2 percent accuracy, the work also claimed to obtained results using Alexnet, Densenet201, InceptionV3 and Googlenet models. Amin et al. [1] used stack sparse autoencoder (SSAE) model to detect tumor as tumors and no tumor. The presented model is evaluated with a number of performance metrics which demonstrates the improved performance. mesut et al. [7] used BrainMRNet model and claimed BrainMRNet is more successful than pretrained CNN models (Alexnet, GoogleNet, VGG-16). The authors used collected datasets by doctors, radiologists and shared on internet with 96% accuracy. Thiruvankadam et al. [4] used BraTS2013 and whole brain atlas datasets and claimed their deep learning approach was better than the conventional state-of-art methods. Fatih et al. [5] used Cancer Genome Atlas Glioblastoma multiform (TCGA-GBM) database with fuzzy C-mean (SR-FCM-CNN) using SqueezeNet architecture (using FCM algorithm).

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IV. FINDINGS AND CONCLUSION

Medical data is indispensable in the field of disease prediction using machine learning. The application of machine learning in the field of detection and diagnosis of abnormality in the data demands learning in the field of detection and diagnosis of abnormality in the data demands learning from available data and further making predictions using the emerging technology of machine learning can be extrapolated by drawing the new methods. machine learning in medical data diagnosis is becoming one of the most promising and growing fields. Brain tumor is the most deadliest tumor where the patient hardly survive more than fourteen months. Therefore, proposing a diagnosis of early stage making the change.

V. REFERENCES

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